

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

AUTOMATION IN TEST DRIVES, THROUGH THE USE OF MONITORED TEST TRACK

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Abstract

This research aims to highlight the road safety training and the deterioration of the only automated driving assessment track in Latin America, situated in Bogotá. This decline is attributed to political differences and the lack of interest from the involved entities. The methodology involves monitoring and chronologically structuring the development of the track, evaluating the results of its implementation, and drawing general conclusions from its deployment. The findings indicate that the track's implementation ensures that drivers who obtain a license possess the necessary skills to operate vehicles safely

Keywords: road safety; Colombia; education; driving license; automatic track.

INTRODUCTION

The increase in the number of vehicles and the bad practices of users has had a significant impact on public health worldwide, resulting in more than 1.3 million deaths and more than 50 million injuries, with low- and middle-income countries making the greatest contribution to the number of people affected [1]. This high number of deaths and injuries has led to great interest on the part of administrations and governmental organisations in trying to address the problem, training users and encouraging campaigns, with the aim of minimising accidents under the goals defined in Sustainable Development Goals 3 "Health and Wellbeing" and 11 "Sustainable Cities and Communities" [2], however, after several years of the definition of the goals, accident figures have not decreased, generating greater pressure and economic expenditure.

Colombia, as a member country of the International Transport Forum, has reflected a strong impact in terms of accidents and road safety, as in the last report delivered, it occupies first place in accident rate out of a total of 34 countries, with a rate of 14.2 deaths per 100,000 inhabitants, surpassing the United States, whose rate is over 12.9 deaths per 100,000 inhabitants [3]. This behaviour, indicative of the year 2021, shows an alarming level of accidents, which has not improved, as the 2022 reports of the national road safety agency indicate that 8,032 citizens died in traffic accidents in the country, with an increase of 13.06% compared to 2021, in which there were 7,104 fatalities [4].

This accident rate has led to the development of road accident and road safety research centres in the country, with the National Road Safety Agency being

the highest representative of analysis and investment in research and prevention in the country, in addition to the different movements and research centres in higher education institutions. Among these is the Universidad Nacional de Colombia, which from its various branches, contributes to the analysis, education and research related to road safety and traffic management issues, focusing on social welfare and sustainable urban development.

Several studies have been conducted on road safety issues, focusing on citizen behaviour [5, p2], statistical analysis [6, p2], injuries [7], road safety audit methodology [8, p1], comparative studies and intervention proposals [9][10], among others, which have contributed greatly to municipal administrations and the fight against accidents. Despite this, some important aspects have been found that have not been properly addressed for the prevention of accidents in Colombia; one of these is the training of motorised users, in which case some shortcomings have been evidenced in terms of the skills required for the operation of vehicles, generating certain doubts regarding teaching methods and in turn the processes of evaluation and licensing. Around the world, there has been an important emphasis on accident prevention through driving assistance or post-training evaluation mechanisms [11][12], characterised by age conditions [13][14]. However, road safety must be considered during the training process of users before, during and after obtaining the licence [15][16], considering that a large number of road accidents are due to inadequate knowledge of driving vehicles, as a result of inadequate training in academies or training centres [17].

The national government has implemented some measures or evaluation criteria for drivers, Resolution 1349 of 2017, where practical and theoretical differentiations are made, in closed environments or public roads, to establish the knowledge requirements of applicants to make use of a vehicle, promoting the proper education and training of users [18]. However, there must be evidence of specific studies in the country on how the exams are carried out. This leads to a general problem where citizens authorised to take the driving tests and their assessment do not have significant control over the authorities, resulting in problems of training and corruption, in which documents are issued without asserting the driver's ability [19].

Based on the identified problems and conflicts, the government took measures regarding the licensing evaluation processes. In 2019, the first guidelines were issued to analyse the possibility of implementing an automated track to evaluate driving skills. However, it was not until 2020 that the project's evaluation, structuring and formulation began [20]. In 2021, After the COVID-19 pandemic, some higher education centres began to be involved as entities responsible for the implementation and operation of the track, allowing the

gathering of the information required for its widespread use and guarantee in driver training, with the inter-administrative contract No. 004 of 2021, which gives approval to the Universidad Nacional for the track's design [21].

Being conceived as the first automated track in Latin America, some topics used in other parts of the world are considered, especially India, which has made a greater contribution to the development of these tracks, confirming the importance of automation and the human factor removal in the process, some examples include the track programming [22], electronics used [17], structure and evaluation system [23], artificial intelligence [24], among others.

The study area is the Universidad Nacional de Colombia campus in Bogotá, the capital district of Colombia (Figure 1), located on the eastern mountain range on the Cundiboyacense plateau at 4°36'35" North latitude and 74°04'54" West longitude. Bogotá has an estimated population 2022 of 7,901,653 inhabitants [25], positioning it as the fifth most populated city in the Americas and a total of 2,525,826 registered vehicles [26].

Figure 1: Bogota Location. Source: authors.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

As a research methodology, the project is reconstructed chronologically, starting with the national government's guidelines, the structuring and construction

of the driver training track, the formulation of the road safety laboratory at the Universidad Nacional de Colombia - Bogotá, and the current condition of the automated track (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Methodology. Source: authors.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As a result of the timeline and follow-up structure, the Nation's provision is taken as a starting point, referring to the beginnings of the need for road safety education and assessment as described below.

National Approach

In 2011, the Colombian Constitutional Court ruled in Ruling C468 of 2011 on the nature of the driving licence, proposing the need to modify the structure for obtaining it, so that access to it would not be considered a right unless the necessary competencies to access it are fulfilled. This ruling establishes that "the activity of

driving a motor vehicle, whether public or private, is in itself a privilege because it cannot be exercised by any person who has the material possibility of getting into a car and driving it, since they must have previously demonstrated that they meet the necessary requirements to do so competently and, consequently, in a safe manner, i.e., that they are familiar with the rules of the road safe, that is to say, that he/she knows the rules that regulate traffic, knows the vehicle, can detect and understand the written messages that the vehicle transmits, is able to decipher the warning or danger messages that are posted on the roads, and has the physical and mental aptitude to drive without endangering his/her fellow human beings" [27]

This decision opened the door to a new form of training and assessment, linking this vision to the national development plan 2011-2021, which promotes the modification of the procedures for obtaining licences, considering the education and training of applicants in the Automotive Education Centres, as well as the mode of assessment, which is subdivided into 2 sections (theoretical and practical), regulated by the Ministry of Transport and executed by external actors, called Driver Recognition Centres [28]. Despite establishing the vision and structuring of the types of tests, it was not until 2017 that how they would be developed was drafted, giving national evidence in Resolution 1349 of 2017 of the Ministry of Transport.

As a result of the resolution's implementation, the licensing conditions of the Logistical Support Evaluation Centres - CALE, as well as the theoretical and practical tests to be taken by applicants for the first time or reclassification, which are based on the guidelines established by the Ibero-American Charter on Driver Licensing, agreed in 2009 as a recognition of the effect of a good licensing in improving road safety [29], are regulated.

On the other hand, in 2018, the government of the day raised the need to continue with the vision of the National Road Safety Plan, highlighting the need for control in driver training and licensing as a measure to mitigate accidents, and this is how in the Bases of the National Development Plan 2018-2022 "*Pact for Colombia, Pact for Equity*" defines the roadmap to review, update and implement a model for training, evaluation, granting, renewal and reclassification of driving licences, ordering the Ministry of Transport and the National Road Safety Agency (ANSV) to implement the project [20]. As a result of this directive, approaches were made to higher education institutions as support entities for research and formulation of the new evaluation mechanisms. However, due to the contingency of the COVID-19 pandemic, the approach was delayed, and the project was suspended until further notice.

Finally, in 2021, the support relationship between the Universidad Nacional de Colombia and the Agencia Nacional de Seguridad Vial is formally structured through inter-administrative contract ANSV-004, which designates the purpose of "*Designing the technological support system and structuring the cost model for the implementation of the theoretical and practical examinations for the licensing of motor vehicle drivers*", thus providing the guidelines required for

the structuring of the automated track [21].

Track Structuring

Once the implementation agreement has been defined, work begins on structuring and compiling information on the track on which the evaluation of the skills and training of the applicants will be carried out; each aptitude to be evaluated focuses on the applicant's correct teaching and ability to use the vehicle without putting other road users at risk. In this sense, the basic concepts and fundamental manoeuvres for the user's performance are studied, considering the Ibero-American Charter on driving licences as a fundamental basis.

For the particular case of the Universidad Nacional, 8 manoeuvres for motorbikes and 5 manoeuvres for cars are structured as the minimum required for the correct performance of driving, which applicants must pass on the track. It should be noted that each of the tests to be developed must be learnt and practised by the applicants within the Automobile Training Centres.

Motorbike testing

Within the evaluation structure of the motorbike user, high speed, low speed and manoeuvrability driving manoeuvres are established, required for the correct performance of the driver; among these are:

Reel-to-reel manoeuvre. As the first manoeuvre to be assessed, the applicant must move the motorbike with the engine switched off, manoeuvring in a limited space forward and backwards, guaranteeing the skills for handling the vehicles without risk of falling or injury to oneself or third parties.

Circular manoeuvre on a limited-width strip. The applicant operates the motorbike at low speed and, without lowering his feet from the footrests, rides over a strip of 6 metres in length and 0.25 metres in width without stopping or leaving the established strip, allowing the driver's skill in manoeuvring the vehicle in movement over confined spaces to be determined.

Low speed slalom manoeuvre. The applicant moves over a 27-metre strip at low speed, less than 30 km/h, activating warning lights and turning right and left, avoiding existing obstacles, and testing the dexterity of vehicle control when making consecutive turns.

Acceleration, clutch and controlled braking manoeuvres. The applicant must control the vehicle over the manoeuvring area, decelerating and applying the brakes until the vehicle stops in the defined space without falling over or overstepping.

Slalom manoeuvre at a minimum speed of 30 km/h and interaction with a U-turn signal. The applicant accelerates the vehicle up to a speed of more than 30 km/h, driving over an initial 40 metres until he/she starts lateral movements to the left and right without hitting the obstacles and without leaving the area delimited for the manoeuvre, nor lowering his/her feet from the footrests; after this, the applicant slows down until reaching the U-turn signal, starting the turn without hitting the obstacles or passing over the delimited area.

Manoeuvre around an obstacle at a minimum speed of 30 km/h and emergency braking. The applicant operates the vehicle at a minimum speed of 50

km/h and a maximum speed of 60 km/h until approaching the obstacle, which he/she must avoid by leaning over without making contact or overstepping the defined area; he/she then moves the vehicle in a straight line by applying the brakes and stopping the motorbike in the defined area without overstepping the space or falling off the vehicle.

Eights-shift manoeuvre. The applicant performs left and right turning manoeuvres over the eight-shaped marked area, activating the corresponding warning lights, maintaining balance using the brake pedal as the only mechanism to stabilise him/herself until completing the course without going beyond the defined area or lowering his/her feet from the footrest.

Manoeuvre interaction with horizontal and vertical traffic signals. The applicant rides the motorbike at a constant speed until 10 metres before the stop sign, at which point he/she must stop 2 metres before the sign without turning the vehicle off or leaving the defined area. The manoeuvre continues until the interaction with the second stop sign and then moves forward to the stop line on the pedestrian crossing, where the manoeuvre ends with the vehicle coming to a complete stop 2 metres from the line and without leaving the delimited area.

Testing for light-duty cars

Within the evaluation structure of the car user, high-speed, low speed and manoeuvrability driving tasks are established, which are essential for the proper performance of the driver.

Forward and stopping manoeuvre. The applicant drives the vehicle over the defined area, stopping at the stop sign and the pedestrian crossing the stop line, following the instructor's instructions until the established circuit has been completed.

Reverse manoeuvre for perpendicular parking. The applicant activates the parking lights, passing the defined area to establish visual sweep and proceeds to park in the defined area, using frontal and reverse movements to maintain adequate spacing on the stripes

parallel to the vehicle.

Turnaround manoeuvre in limited spacing. The applicant must change the vehicle's direction, activating the warning lights without going beyond the defined area and ending with the vehicle in the opposite direction to the one it entered.

Right and left in-line parking manoeuvre. To assess his/her skills in parallel parking, the applicant shall position the vehicle to the right and left, activating the warning lights and not exceeding the defined area.

Interaction manoeuvres with a stop sign with traffic lights. The applicant shall drive the vehicle in the defined area, stop the vehicle when the traffic light signal indicates it, and start the movement when the light indicates green.

Stop/start ramp manoeuvre. The applicant shall be able to move forward, stop and continue moving on a ramped corridor without moving backwards or leaving the defined area.

Regarding technological requirements, space and measurement parameters, consultations and estimates were made in the field, considering the existing knowledge in other parts of the world, especially India, which has a greater experience and information record, thus identifying the type of software and hardware needed [17], structure and evaluation system [23][30], as well as general dimensions of the space required.

The implementation area was structured within the university grounds, as shown in Figure 3, making use of the internal road corridor, modifying the sectors with deficiencies or space requirements, and limiting the sector for the circulation of users who do not use the runway. In addition, the necessary signage is structured to ensure the safety of users and the runway, following the guidelines defined in the Colombian Road Signage Manual in force, considering colors, retro-reflection, distance and other necessary parameters [31]. As a result of the proposed signage and structuring, Figure 4 is presented.

Figure 3: Location Universidad Nacional de Colombia. Source: authors.

At the same time, the on-road assessment track is structured, which aims to teach and assess the skills of candidates when faced with real traffic conditions, thus allowing them to understand the dynamics of mobility and its interaction with traffic signals. Among the tests to be evaluated on public roads for light cars and motorbikes are the following:

Traffic manoeuvre on a straight road, turning at an intersection. The applicant shall drive in the centre of the lane, keeping the corresponding lateral and frontal distance, and maintain an appropriate speed according to the flow conditions without exceeding the limits defined on the road.

Turning manoeuvres at junctions or intersections. While driving on the road, the applicant makes two left turns at intersections and two right turns at intersections and roundabouts that the applicant encounters during the test; he/she must follow the following sequence: observation, signalling and manoeuvre.

Interaction manoeuvre with horizontal and vertical signals. While driving, the driver must demonstrate that he/she knows and respects the traffic police signs, temporary and work signs, traffic lights, and vertical and horizontal signs.

To preserve the laboratory environment, the Universidad Nacional structures the manoeuvring evaluation track on public roads inside the campus, considering that the mobility dynamics of users inside the premises behave in the same way as in an external environment, thus structuring the corridor shown in Figure 5, following the road signs in force, guaranteeing the control of applicants and maintaining the safety of road users.

Start of operations

After several months of research, review and design, the automated track was consolidated and structured, giving its official opening of the Universidad Nacional de Colombia's Road Safety Laboratory on 22 July 2022, achieving great social impact and with the participation of the Ministry of Transport, the National Road Safety Agency committee and various national media.

The track's deployment allowed the collection of data related to how applicants approach the tests and the capabilities of each one to ensure the safety of road users; likewise, it enables the evaluation of the instructors of the Automotive Training Centres, which guarantees the proper training of applicants in the training centres. Each of these aspects identified in the automated track provides strong support in the training of drivers, which translates into a possible reduction of road accidents.

On the other hand, the opening of the research centre, including the automated track, has allowed the training of professionals who study at the university to be consolidated, providing different perspectives and knowledge for their development in training fields such as Traffic Engineering, Road Safety Audits, Road Signalling, among others.

As a result of the track implementation and requirements assessment of its implementation, a draft resolution was available as support for the acceptance and structuring at a national level of the Logistical Support Centres of Evaluation, where the theoretical and practical elements are to be evaluated. The minimum passing scores are defined. However, after its dissemination, the official document that would comply with the guidelines must be structured.

Government change

On 7 August 2022, President Iván Duque Márquez's term of office came to an end, giving way to the current President Gustavo Francisco Petro Urrego for the period 2022 - 2026, a change that led to various perceptions and uncertainties regarding the continuity of the processes being carried out during the 2018 - 2022 term of office; During this transition period, the Universidad Nacional continued with the research and testing process on the automated track and the public road track, however, after several months of uncertainty, the current government did not make any pronouncement regarding the continuity of the project, thus giving a critical blow to the vision of driver training in order to improve road safety that was intended to be carried out.

Figure 4: Automated test track signalling. Source: authors.

Figura 5: Public road test. Source: authors.

The National Road Safety Agency, as the entity in charge of the project, has left it aside in order to focus the limited existing resources on priority issues and immediate action, leaving the National University as the last lifeline of the project as the operator of the road safety laboratory; However, given the lack of funding

for higher education, the university had to suspend the research processes of the automated track, because its operating costs could not be covered by the institution, leaving a significant deterioration of the test area in 2023, as shown in Figures 6, and 7.

Figure 6: Current state of the track (1). Source: authors.

Figure 7: Current state of the track (2). Source: authors.

Concluding thoughts

After several years of study and dedication on the part of the entities involved, the abandonment of a project with great contributions to national road safety education, in addition to generating a starting point for neighbouring and Latin American nations on how to evaluate candidates for driving licences, has caused some dissatisfaction; all this under the bureaucratic problems of the governments in power, in which they proceed with their horizons and do not consider or delay projects of great importance coming from previous governments.

On the other hand, structuring this type of track allows for improving the quality of the users that perform on the roads. Despite this, there are some differences regarding how they are structured, for example, the existing tracks in India, in which the number of manoeuvres and structure can vary [23][30+](Puppala, 2013, Governance Knowledge Centre, 2011). However, one must be aware of each place's cultural differences and particular needs. Therefore, the definition of automated tracks must consider particular studies and not the exact replication of what exists in the environment.

The training and evaluation processes that are achieved with the implementation of the automated track allow for structuring a road safety education project for the future that guarantees proper road discipline and, therefore, a reduction in the accident rate, all this under the training mission of higher institutions, which in their dissemination process, facilitate its scope, however, funding problems limit the processes, and therefore solutions must be sought to ensure preservation over time.

Finally, the project's revival will allow research to continue, trying to evaluate user conditions and mobility patterns that will lead to mechanisms for the reduction of accident rates. However, the government's willingness to strengthen research on these issues is necessary.

Conclusions

Research at the national level is important as it allows the establishment of synergetic relationships in

search of common results, as in the case of road safety, trying to minimise accidents and improve mobility conditions in the territory.

The condition of funding research projects should be considered a priority regardless of the government of the day, allowing the continuity of processes of great importance and minimising the loss of resources due to the inoperability of the research and the elements involved in it.

Structuring automated driver assessment lanes improves road safety conditions by guaranteeing that users circulating in the territory have the required skills to carry them out. In addition, it removes the human factor in decision-making and licence allocation, which can be subject to corruption, leading to an increased risk of accidents.

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